

INVESTIGATION ABOUT FRACTURE MODE AND STRENGTH IN CURVED SECTION OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

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1 Introduction

With the environmental issues become more serious, in order to improve fuel efficiency of mass production automobile, applying CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) to the vehicle body is considered to reduce weight of vehicles because of their potential of low cost and high cycle production. Compared to conventional CFRTPS (carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resins), CFRTP is surely superior in not only high-cycle molding, jointing, recycling but also in complex shape molding. Polypropylene (PP) is one of the thermoplastics with significant productivity and environmental durability. PP has attracted great attention on automotive application and providing a wide range of application. The random arrangement of carbon fibers gives the composite material high production efficiency and considerable recycling ability. So, introduce the random carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene into automobile production is regarded as a feasible mean to mitigate environmental and energy problems [1, 2].

To meet the extensive application of CF/PP (carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene) in mass produced transportation, the suitability of CF/PP for complex shapes is taken into account. More specifically, whether CF/PP is suitable for the design of a curved part such as thin-walled hollow structural member and jointed flanges are considered seriously.

As the CF/PP is a novel material, it remains unclear about the strength and fracture mode in the curved section of the CF/PP. The curved section is also regarded as the weak point of structures. Under current researches, the strength and fracture of curved section are greatly affected by the effects of tensile strength, compressive strength and interlaminar tensile strength of the material. CFRTP, considered as an anisotropic material, the interlaminar tensile strength is different from the

tensile strength well as compressive strength. So, to ensure the usability of CF/PP on automobile production, it is necessary to figure out the relationship between the fracture modes and strength types.

A lot of attempts have been made to develop test methods for measuring the interlaminar mechanical properties [3-10]. Among those test methods, the interlaminar tensile strength at curved section is regarded important not only in mechanical aspects but also in the production side and applications [4, 5, 7, 9, and 10].

This paper is focusing on evaluating the strength and fracture behavior in the curved section of the CF/PP which consists of short random carbon fiber and polypropylene. Tensile test of L-shaped CF/PP has been conducted. Under finite-element analysis, the finite-element model is supported by the experimental characterization, and the stress distribution at the curved section of specimens is calculated. After that, the relationship between the fracture mode, strength and the curvature of curved section is discussed.

2 Material and experimental procedure

2.1 Materials

The composite material CF/PP is composed of short carbon fiber with an average length in 6mm and polypropylene films. The carbon fibers are random orientated into the film to form the material used in this study. Both the carbon fiber and polypropylene are provided by TORAY INDUSTRIES, INC.

2.2 Specimens

The curved beam CF/PP specimens were manufactured by heat-and-cool pressing technology, which is one of the press molding techniques. Through the molding process, the CF/PP sheets in

35mm width were heated up to 220°C by infrared heater and the L-shaped molds (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) are also heated to 150°C. Then, the material was set into the mold and the mold was cooled down with compressive pressed from 150°C to 85°C in 10MPa pressure on the material by hydraulic-controlled pressing machine. After that, unload the pressure and remove the specimen. The molding process of specimens demonstrated as Fig. 3. Three specimen sizes are conducted in this study, and to insure the accuracy of the experiment, three specimens are manufactured for each radius. Detailed dimensions of the specimens are shown in Table 1. Specimens are same in width $w = 35\text{mm}$ and thickness $t = 2\text{mm}$. The three different kinds of inner and outer radius of the specimens are, $r_i = 3$ and $r_o = 5$, $r_i = 5$ and $r_o = 7$, $r_i = 10$ and $r_o = 12$, respectively. The geometric parameters of the specimens are shown in Fig. 4.

2.3 Experimental procedure

Schematics of the L-shaped tensile test illustrated in Fig. 5. The specimens were fixed in a special fixture, and a universal testing machine was used to conduct the tensile test. The load cell is set to 5kN with a measuring accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$. The tensile displacement rate was set at the speed of 1.0 mm/min during the loading process. Loads and displacements are recorded digitally by the testing machine until the failure occurred on the specimen.

2.4 Finite element analysis

A 2D finite-element model was used on the curved beam specimen to verify the relationship between load and displacement well as to analysis the stress distribution in the curved section of the CF/PP. Only a half size model of the bending test specimen was needed due to the symmetry geometric theory; the normal direction of the symmetry plane was constrained in y direction. The specimen was fixed to both sides of the contact face of the loading fixture, and the loading was added to the fixture at a rotation free hinge (Fig. 5). Abaqus 6.11 was used to support the analysis, and material direction 1, 2 and 3 were determined as illustrated in Fig. 5. The direction 1 was parallel to the longitudinal direction of the beam; the direction 2 was parallel to the thickness direction of the beam, in other words, perpendicular to the longitudinal direction; and the direction 3 was perpendicular to the plane 1-2. For the orientation of the 6mm-length carbon fiber contained in the material show strong randomness, the specimen was considered as a planar isotropic material. The material properties respectively along

directions 1, 2 and 3 were determined as indicated in Table. 2. All elements were four-nodded quadrilateral with 20 elements in the thickness direction of the specimen model, also the effect of nonlinearity was considered due to deformation occurred during the test.

3 Results

3.1 Tensile test

The load-displacement curves of specimens with the radius $r_i = 3$ (Fig. 6), $r_i = 5$ (Fig. 7) and $r_i = 10$ (Fig. 8) are given respectively. The load-displacement curves recorded the relationship between load and the specimen displacement under load till the specimen was failed. For specimens of each radius, the failure occurred at almost the same load, and variation of displacements at the failure of the three specimens is small. This small variation of the characterization at the failure of the specimens means the variation of the material strength at curved section is small. By comparing Fig. 6, Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 and under comprehensive consideration of loading force and bending radius of specimens, a positive correlation was demonstrated between them. That is, the loading force strengthens obviously from about 400N to 800N with the radius of specimens increase from 3mm to 10mm.

Photos of the failure situation of specimens in different radius were taken after the experiment; the photos of breakage of curved sections are illustrated in Fig. 9. In the photos, specimens with different radius showed different fracture modes in curved sections. For specimens with $r_i = 3$ and $r_i = 5$, the failure mode of the curved section was delamination fracture (Fig. 9, left and middle), relatively, for the specimens with $r_i = 10$, the failure mode behaved as tensile fracture at the inner side of curved section (Fig. 9, right). Also comparing the specimens with $r_i = 3$ and $r_i = 5$, the range of delamination of $r_i = 5$ is wider than that of $r_i = 3$.

3.2 Finite element analytical results

Finite-element analytical results were compared to the results of the experimental tests and separately illustrated in Fig. 10 ($r_i = 3$), Fig. 11 ($r_i = 5$) and Fig. 12 ($r_i = 10$). The experimental results are presented by load-displacement curves and the FEA results are presented by the plots. In general, the results of finite-element analysis shows a satisfying agreement with the experimental results related to all of the

curves, which certificate the correctness of finite-element model.

The maximum stress, minimum stress and distribution of stress of the specimens are calculated by computer based on the finite-element model simulation, respectively. The distribution of tangential stress (tensile/compressive stress) and radial stress (interlaminar tensile stress) are calculated and drew separately. The tangential stress distribution of specimens with inner radius $r_i = 3$, $r_i = 5$ and $r_i = 10$ are illustrated in Fig. 13, Fig. 14 and Fig. 15, respectively. The specimens with $r_i = 10$, which failed in the test in tensile fracture, shows the most serious tangential stress concentration and the largest tangential stress at the inner side of the curved section, in contrast, the tangential stress concentration in specimens with $r_i = 3$ and $r_i = 5$ emerge at smaller regions and the maximum tangential stress is relatively small. To the radial stress distribution, the results are analogous to the tangential stress distribution. As the specimens with $r_i = 3$ and $r_i = 5$ show more serious stress concentration around the mid-plane of the curved section with the largest radial stress as their failure mode is delamination fracture (Fig. 16, Fig. 17), and the specimens with $r_i = 10$ shows slight radial stress concentration and lower maximum radial stress (Fig. 18).

By summarizing the maximum tangential stress and radial stress of the specimens (Fig. 19, Fig. 20), the composite tensile strength and interlaminar tensile strength at curved section can be predicted. The figure shows that the maximum tensile strength and the maximum interlaminar tensile strength are emerging at specimens with $r_i = 10$ and $r_i = 3$ respectively, and the value of each strength can be predicted to 327MPa and 21MPa separately.

4 Discussions

Considering with the results gave from the experiment and the finite-element analysis, the geometric dimensions of the specimens showed great effect to the interlaminar tensile stress (radial stress). The reason is because the curvature is small at the curved section in the small radius specimen, and the normal stress difference through the curved surface of the specimen is bigger when the curvature is small. Therefore, the interlaminar tensile stress concentration appears more obvious around the mid-plane of the curved section, which can lead to delamination. So, the results show that when the

curvature radius becomes smaller, interlaminar stress becomes larger comparatively, and because the maximum interlaminar tensile strength is quite low in CF/PP materials, hence interlaminar fracture occurs before compressive fracture. In other words, if corner part is designed with tensile or compressive strength, the section destructs at an unexpected lower load when its curvature radius is small. This phenomenon cannot be observed in metallic materials, so we have to be careful about this minimum radius of composite materials.

By performing three radiuses of L-shaped tensile tests, both interlaminar tensile strength and net tensile strength can be obtained. The minimum radius which avoids delamination can be calculated by the relationship between the radiuses and two strengths.

In addition, the interlaminar tensile strength of the CF/PP composites, which predicted to be 21MPa, is almost the same as that of the polypropylene resin itself [11, 12]. Accordingly, we can also calculate easily the minimum radius of CF/PP composites by using only normal flexural test and resin strength.

Table 1 Specimens types and dimensions.

	A	B	C
r_i [mm]	3	5	10
r_o [mm]	5	7	12
t [mm]	2	2	2
w [mm]	35	35	35
N (Number of tests)	3	3	3

Table 2 Material parameter settings.

Material properties	CMT (CF/PP)	
Elastic modulus (GPa)	E_1	14.0
	E_2	2.0
	E_3	14.0
	G_{12}	1.0
	G_{13}	4.0
	G_{23}	1.0
Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	0.2
	ν_{13}	0.3
	ν_{23}	0.2

Fig. 1 Front view (upper) and lateral view of L-shaped mold drawing and detailed dimensions.

Fig.2 Mold 3D model (left) and the sectional view (right).

Fig.3 Molding process of the specimens.

Fig.4 Schematics of L-shaped tensile test (left) and geometric parameters of the specimen (right).

Fig.5 Finite-element model.

Fig.6 Experiment results of specimen with r_i of 3 mm.

Fig.7 Experiment results of specimen with r_i of 5 mm.

Fig.8 Experiment results of specimen with r_i of 10 mm.

Fig.9 Side view after the experiment of a specimen with r_i of 3mm (left), a specimen with r_i of 5mm (middle) and a specimen with r_i of 10mm (right).

Fig.10 Results comparison between experiment and FEM of specimens with r_i of 3mm.

Fig.11 Results comparison between experiment and FEM of specimens with r_i of 5mm.

Fig.14 Tangential stress σ_θ [MPa] distribution at failure of specimens with r_i of 5mm.

Fig.12 Results comparison between experiment and FEM of specimens with r_i of 10mm.

Fig.15 Tangential stress σ_θ [MPa] distribution at failure of specimens with r_i of 10mm.

Fig.13 Tangential stress σ_θ [MPa] distribution at failure of specimens with r_i of 3mm.

Fig.16 Radial stress σ_r [MPa] distribution at failure of specimens with r_i of 3mm.

Fig.17 Radial stress σ_r [MPa] distribution at failure of specimens with r_i of 5mm.

Fig.18 Radial stress σ_r [MPa] distribution at failure of specimens with r_i of 10mm.

Fig.19 Tangential stress at failure σ_θ [MPa] of the specimens with different radius.

Fig.20 Radial stress at failure σ_r [MPa] of the specimens with different radius.

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